

WETLAND AESTHETICS VERSUS WETLAND FUNCTION

TEACHING PROTOCOL

GRADE LEVEL: Secondary school

LESSON STRUCTURE: min. 1 school lesson for Introduction ("Engage" – Activity),
min. 2 school lessons for field trip ("Explore"- Activity Photo Safari)
min. 1 school lesson for providing background information on aesthetic perception and reflecting on photos ("Explain" & "Elaborate"- Activities)

INTRODUCTION:

Floodplains are vital ecosystems that provide a wide range of ecosystem services essential to ecological health, economic resilience, and social well-being. This learning experience guides students through a multidimensional exploration of floodplains, highlighting their ecological functions, the influence of aesthetic perceptions on our attitudes, and the challenges of conservation and restoration. Students will explore both the visible and less obvious benefits of floodplains, engage with landscape preferences, and critically reflect on how these perceptions influence environmental decision-making. The activities are designed to foster environmental awareness, encourage empathy for natural processes, and deepen understanding of the complex relationship between beauty, function, and ecological value. Although floodplains may not always appear visually appealing, they play a crucial role in supporting biodiversity and sustaining ecosystems. Aesthetic values and personal attachments strongly influence how people respond to environmental change. Recognizing this connection is key to promoting effective and socially accepted restoration of natural habitats like wetlands and floodplains.

KEYWORDS: Ecosystem services, Wetland functions, Aesthetic perception, Landscape preferences

LEARNING OBJECTIVES:

By the end of this lesson, students will be able to:

- 1 Explain the ecosystem services approach
- 2 Identify typical ecosystem services provided by wetlands.
- 3 Differentiate between natural and human-made environments
- 4 Understand the basis of aesthetic perceptions and landscape preferences

- 5 Reflect on their personal aesthetic perceptions (reflection)
- 6 Analyze how personal and societal attitudes shape environmental decisions, particularly in floodplain restoration projects (critical thinking skills)
- 7 Appreciate the importance of floodplains and foster environmental stewardship and awareness

TEACHING FRAMEWORK BASED ON THE 5E INSTRUCTIONAL MODEL

1. ENGAGE - Sparking curiosity

AIM: Introduction to ecosystem services of wetlands

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- What are ecosystem services?
- Which ecosystem services do natural wetlands provide?
- How does wetland degradation affect the provision of ecosystem services?

TEACHER SUPPORT

MATERIALS NEEDED: Photos of regional river and floodplain landscapes

ACTIVITY OVERVIEW:

1 PRESENT THE ECOSYSTEM SERVICES CONCEPT USING PICTURES OF RIVERS AND/OR FLOODPLAINS.

Discuss the three primary types of ecosystem services: provisioning, regulating, and cultural. (Haines-Young, 2023).

2 ENCOURAGE STUDENTS TO BRAINSTORM THE ECOSYSTEM SERVICES PROVIDED BY FLOODPLAINS.

Collect and categorize these services on flipchart papers. Examples include:

- Provisioning services: Floodplains provide resources such as freshwater, fertile soils for agriculture, raw materials like reeds or timber, food like fish, ...
- Regulating services: Floodplains play a crucial role in regulating water cycles, mitigating flood risks, filtering pollutants, and storing carbon, thereby contributing to climate change adaptation and mitigation.
- Cultural services: Floodplains also offer recreational opportunities, inspire art and culture, and hold historical or spiritual significance for many communities.

3 IDENTIFY AND DISCUSS POTENTIAL HUMAN-INDUCED THREATS OR DAMAGES TO THE ECOSYSTEM SERVICES OF FLOODPLAINS.

Document them on a separate flipchart.

4 USE THE *RESTORE4LIFE INTERACTIVE ILLUSTRATION* FOR THIS TOPIC OR PLAY THE *RESTORE4LIFE WETLAND FRESK GAME* TO REINFORCE WHAT HAS BEEN LEARNED IN A PLAYFUL MANNER.

MATERIALS FOR STUDENTS (OPTIONAL):

Computers or smartphones, literature search links, and instructions on searching for and evaluating trustworthy resources.

NOTE: Avoid introducing prior knowledge about aesthetic perception or landscape preferences at this stage to prevent influencing the “Explore” activity.

2. EXPLORE – Hands-on learning activity

PHOTO SAFARI: “MY FAVORITE SPOT”

AIM: Develop an understanding of the differences between “natural” and “human-made” (wetland) environments.

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- Which landscape elements do you find beautiful, and which do you find ugly?
- Do all people perceive landscapes in the same way?
- Are beautiful places in nature also functional?

ACTIVITY OVERVIEW:

This activity enables students to reflect on their perception of landscapes, environmental aesthetics, and the impact of human activity on natural areas.

OUTDOOR – PART:

1 PLAN AN EXCURSION:

Organize a walk along a route that includes diverse landscape elements and visible signs of human influence (e.g., along a watercourse, through a floodplain area).

2 FORM SMALL GROUPS

Divide students into groups of 2–4 participants.

3 PHOTOGRAPH BEAUTIFUL & UGLY LOCATIONS:

Each group selects spots they consider beautiful and spots they find ugly and photographs them. Optionally, they can use a cardboard photo frame to artistically “frame” each scene.

INDOOR – PART:

4 PHOTO SELECTION AT HOME:

Each group selects three photos from each category (beautiful and ugly).

5 GROUP DISCUSSION:

Facilitate a discussion in which each group shares their selected photos and explains their choices. What makes a place beautiful or ugly to them? Let students explain their choices and opinions in their own words.

6 REFLECTION ON PERCEPTION:

Which photos do most students see as beautiful? Which ones are seen as ugly? Which photos show the biggest differences in how students see them? Are there any patterns or shared ideas? Use the photos taken to explain that “beautiful” does not always mean “natural” or “ecologically functional.”

3. EXPLAIN – Making sense of the experiences

AIM: Understand the underlying factors that shape our aesthetic perceptions of landscapes and reflect on personal preferences in relation to landscape function, particularly in wetland areas.

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- Why do we find certain places in nature attractive or not?
- How are aesthetic preferences connected to wetland functions and ecosystem services?

TEACHER SUPPORT

MATERIALS NEEDED: Example images illustrating the three main dimensions of landscape preference. (Use provided images in the students' worksheet or substitute with regionally relevant photographs)

ACTIVITY OVERVIEW:

1 INTRODUCE BACKGROUND CONCEPTS:

Begin with a short presentation or explanation of the key concepts behind landscape aesthetics and preferences. Emphasize that our perceptions are shaped by:

- Evolutionary factors (e.g., preference for open spaces, water, or shelter)
- Socio-cultural influences (e.g., traditions, media, education)
- Individual experiences (e.g., personal memories, emotional connections)

2 CATEGORIZE EXAMPLE PHOTOS:

Present several landscape images and sort them into categories based on aesthetic theory. Encourage students to explain their categorizations.

3 CLASSROOM DISCUSSION:

Facilitate a discussion using the sorted images. Guide students to reflect on

- What makes a landscape attractive?
- How do human influences (e.g., buildings, litter, pathways) alter perceptions?
- How do aesthetic values relate to ecological function and ecosystem services?

4 REVISIT "MY FAVORITE SPOT" PHOTOS:

Have students re-examine the photographs they took during the earlier activity.

Ask them to assess their chosen locations through the lens of landscape aesthetic theory:

- Do their preferences align with known aesthetic principles?
- Has their perception changed after learning more about the topic?

BACKGROUND INFORMATION ON LANDSCAPE AESTHETICS AND PREFERENCES:

Theories of landscape preference are based on three dimensions: biological/evolutionary, social/cultural, and individual (e.g., Vygotsky, 1978; Bourassa, 1991).

BIOLOGICAL/EVOLUTIONARY PERSPECTIVE: Humans prefer landscapes that ensure survival, providing food and shelter. Open, savanna-like landscapes with vantage points were advantageous for hunting, while forested areas and shelters offered protection. Water bodies were crucial for survival, influencing settlement patterns near rivers, lakes, or seas (e.g., Orians, 1986; Appleton, 1975). Today, we still value these features—open plains, viewpoints, and water bodies (see Fig. 1)—while feeling uneasy in disordered, unclear spaces (see Fig. 2). Additionally, people have different preferences and aversions toward types of landscapes depending on their origins and personal histories. Mountain dwellers often find flatlands too vast and monotonous, while those living in the plains feel confined in the valleys of the Alps.

SOCIAL/CULTURAL DIMENSION: Landscape elements that signal group belonging are preferred (Bourassa, 1991). This dimension evolves over generations and includes cultural symbols like Christian landscape features (church towers, shrines) or national symbols (e.g., alpine meadows). Aesthetic appreciation depends on comparisons between familiar and new landscapes.

INDIVIDUAL DIMENSION: Shaped by personal development (e.g., knowledge level, life stage, experiences), each person has unique landscape aesthetics (Bourassa, 1991), which may change over time. This dimension includes ecological awareness, recognizing the ecological value of landscapes with knowledge about ecosystem functions and naturalness. Environmental education helps see ecological elements like deadwood or “swampy” meadows positively. Environmental education in schools can, therefore, help us see deadwood in water (Fig. 2) not as disorder or dirt but as a habitat, and thus view it positively. The same applies to other ecologically valuable landscape elements, such as “swampy” floodplain meadows (important for flood retention, habitat for semi-terrestrial plants and animals) or stagnant, “dirty” ponds (essential habitats for amphibian development).

Fig. 3 Example images for naturalness, ecological value, and human perception (evolutionary and social dimension) (copyright: WCL)

Fig. 1: Regulated floodplain area
Naturalness: -
Ecological value: +/-
Aesthetic Perception: +++
(Water, open view, inviting, viewpoint, human traces)

Abb. 2: Unmodified floodplain area with deadwood and ponds
Naturalness: +++
Ecological value: +++
Aesthetic Perception: -
(Cluttered, messy, dirty, evolutionary and social dimension)

Abb. 3: Near-natural stream section
Naturalness: ++
Ecological value: +++
Aesthetic Perception: ++
(It does not appear threatening to most people, and is perceived as beautiful because of/ despite the diverse flow patterns, evolutionary and social dimension)

4. EXTEND / ELABORATE – Expanding understanding

AIM: Understand how personal and societal attitudes influence environmental decisions -especially in the context of floodplain restoration- and foster a deeper appreciation for the ecological importance of wetlands.

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- How do we benefit from wetland restoration?
- Is the attractiveness of a habitat a problem for wetland restoration?

TEACHER SUPPORT

MATERIALS NEEDED: Photos of regional river and floodplain landscapes ranging from natural to highly degraded.

ACTIVITY OVERVIEW:

*TITLE: BEAUTIFUL VERSUS FUNCTIONAL:
IS THIS A PROBLEM FOR WETLAND RESTORATION?*

1 DISTRIBUTE LANDSCAPE PHOTOS:

Provide students with a set of example images showing a range of river and floodplain environments:

- Natural wetland habitats and dynamic structures (e.g., fallen trees, flood debris, deadwood)
- River engineering structures (e.g., ripraps, levees, dams, ...)
- Degraded wetland habitats
- Human “imitations” of nature (artificial yet aesthetically pleasing environments, e.g., parks with aquatic habitats)

2 CATEGORIZATION TASK:

Ask students to categorize the example images into three categories: natural, slightly influenced by humans, or strongly influenced by humans.

3 ANALYZE PREFERENCES:

Have students analyze their preferences and aversions to specific landscape elements in the photos, exploring the biological, social, and individual factors behind these feelings. Discuss potential gender-specific or cultural differences within the group.

4 DISCUSS ECOLOGICAL FUNCTION VS. AESTHETIC VALUE:

Highlight the ecological value of elements that are often perceived as ugly or messy, such as deadwood (habitat and nursery for numerous beneficial organisms), leaf piles (winter shelter for hedgehogs), or wild floodplain meadows (home to rare plants and insects). Discuss how human-made structures may be more attractive than some natural structures and how this can influence political decisions on wetland restoration.

5 REFLECT ON RESTORATION CHALLENGES

Guide students in exploring how aesthetic preferences can influence public and political support for restoration projects:

- Why might people oppose natural floodplain restoration?
- How do strong emotional or cultural attachments to a familiar (but ecologically poor) landscape affect environmental decision-making?
- What can be done to reframe perceptions and communicate the value of “messy” or wild nature?

5. EVALUATE – Assessing learning

AIM: Assess students' understanding of floodplain ecosystems, the role of aesthetic perception, and the complexity of environmental decision-making. This phase also promotes personal reflection and synthesis of learning.

ESSENTIAL AND GUIDING QUESTIONS:

- Did the students reach the learning objectives?
- Can they apply their knowledge to real-world situations and articulate different

TEACHER SUPPORT

SUGGESTED EVALUATION ACTIVITY: ROLE-PLAY DEBATE

TITLE: *SHOULD WE RESTORE THE WETLAND?*

SCENARIO:

A proposal has been introduced to restore a nearby floodplain that is currently used for recreation and agriculture. Students assume the roles of various stakeholders in a town hall-style debate.

STAKEHOLDER ROLES MAY INCLUDE:

Environmental conservationist, Urban planner, Local resident, Landowner, Farmer, Ecotourism entrepreneur, Municipal policymaker, Youth climate activist, Scientist, or Ecologist

PREPARATION:

- Assign or let students choose roles.
- Provide time for each group to research and prepare their arguments.
- Encourage them to consider both aesthetic values and ecological functions.
- Optional: Give each role a short background card with main concerns, interests, and values.

DEBATE FOCUS:

- What are the pros and cons of restoring the floodplain?
- How do different values (beauty, function, economy, identity) affect decisions?
- Can a compromise or shared solution be reached?

ALTERNATIVE ONLINE ROLE PLAY SUGGESTION (in german only):

"Moneris Mayor" <https://monerismayor.igb-berlin.de/>

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AUTHORS: EVA FELDBACHER, CLARA ROSENBERGER, GABRIELE WEIGELHOFER - BOKU University

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WORKSHEET - EXPLORE

PHOTO SAFARI: "MY FAVORITE SPOT"

MATERIALS NEEDED:

- smartphone or camera;
- cardboard photo frame (optional – to frame the photo locations)

INSTRUCTIONS:

- 1 Work in small groups of 2-4 people.

OUTDOOR – PART:

- 2 Follow the route shown by your teacher.
- 3 As a group, photograph places you find beautiful and places you find ugly. Use the cardboard photo frame if you'd like to add a creative touch.

INDOOR / BACK IN THE CLASSROOM:

- 4 Choose three photos from each category (beautiful and ugly).
- 5 In a group discussion, explain your choices:
 - Why did you find some places beautiful?
 - What made others ugly?
 - What emotions, memories, or associations influenced your decisions?

AUTHORS: GABRIELE WEIGELHOFER, EVA FELDBACHER, CLARA ROSENBERGER - BOKU University

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WORKSHEET - EXPLAIN

LANDSCAPE AESTHETICS AND PREFERENCES

Look at the images and rate each one for its:

- Naturalness
- Ecological Value
- Attractiveness

Use the numbers **1 to 5** to rate each image (1 very low, 2 low, 3 neutral/unclear, 4 high, 5 very high).

Then, try to identify which of the three dimensions of landscape preference (**evolutionary, socio-cultural, and individual**) had the biggest influence on your perception.

- Was your judgment shaped more by evolutionary preferences, e.g. open view, water supply, safety?
- Did socio-cultural influences play a role, e.g. media, traditions, education?
- Or was it based on personal/individual experiences, e.g. childhood memories, emotions, places you know?

IMAGE	NATURALNESS	ECOLOGICAL VALUE	ATTRACTIVENESS	DIMENSION
1				
2				
3				

Image 1

Image2

Image 3

AUTHORS: EVA FELDBACHER, CLARA ROSENBERGER, GABRIELE WEIGELHOFER
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